

DUCT TAPE AND DOWNLOADS: DIGITAL PRESERVATION ON A BUDGET

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Abstract - Digital Preservation can sound like something that's only being done by the big and well funded organisations, but there are things you can do to extend the life of your digital collection without needing to spend a great deal of money. This tutorial will present a number of tools and options that demonstrate some of the open source tools you can use to get started in preserving your digital materials on a tiny budget. To cater to a variety of different technical skills, the tutorial will not expect attendees to have the tools installed for use in the session. However, pre-tutorial materials will be provided and those interested can install the applications to follow along or come prepared with their questions.

Submission Type - Please select 1 submission type: Tutorial

Keywords - Please indicate up to 5 keywords, separated by commas. Open source software, Preservation tools, Skills

Conference Topics - Please select 1 conference topic: Haerenga - Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

Many small collecting organisations feel they are unable to even begin their journey of preserving the digital material in their collections because they lack significant budgets or technical skills. While big government funded archives have multi-year and multi-million dollar projects, smaller organisations sometimes only have a surplus of volunteers and time.

Most monolithic Digital Preservation Systems make use of a number of small, open source tools to

identify, virus scan, normalise (convert), and store their digital collections. Without the "monolithic" component that ties these tools together, they are still able to be freely used and sometimes people-power can be harnessed to process, describe, and link a collection of digital files to their collection management system - whether that be a behemoth itself, or a folder of spreadsheets.

II. INTENDED AUDIENCE

At Gaia Resources we've used these open source tools in implementing large Digital Preservation Systems. We hope this tutorial will help smaller collecting organisations with limited budgets but a willingness to make a start on preserving their digital collections.

People from larger collecting organisations with existing monolithic digital preservation systems may also find this session useful to explain the various open source tools that are used by their systems, and consider how they might make use of these in manual workflows.

III. WHAT YOU WILL LEARN

This tutorial will provide attendees with information on using a range of open source tools - including why we use them, what they do, and how to use them. We will introduce multiple tools, but focus in on a small selection for a more practical demonstration:

- How to choose tools;
- Pre preservation file checks - virus checks;
- File format identification;
- Format validation;
- Transcoding video and audio files and normalising images;
- Packaging and storing files;
- Storage options and fixity;
- Ongoing stewardship and other resources.

IV. COME PREPARED

Details of the software we will be using will be made available before the conference for anyone who wants to pre-install these, and also some notes for attendees to reference afterwards. We can also offer an online video meeting to be held prior to the conference for any attendees who would like to have any specific questions addressed, and to help us understand the background of those who are coming along.

Attendees may wish to bring their laptops along and make sure they have sufficient privileges to be able to install software. However, this is not a requirement and the tutorial will be formatted as a presentation. This is to ensure we can cater to differing technical abilities without troubleshooting becoming the main focus.

V. STRUCTURE

The format will be a tutorial with Meg & Sarah presenting on the use of free, open source tools which anyone can use to get started in the world of digital preservation. The session will run for three hours and accommodate two short breaks. If possible, we'd love to cater to online and in person attendees. We envision delivering the material in a classroom like environment where we can share and present screens to demonstrate the skills and tools we discuss. We would also be happy for this session to be recorded for future viewing by interested parties.

VI. CONCLUSION

The tools that we are discussing in this tutorial are used at all scales of digital preservation. We believe that this session will help some of the smaller collecting organisations make good and achievable first steps in their journeys to preserve their digital collections.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Meg Travers worked in digital roles in government archives, libraries, and museums in Western Australia before joining Gaia Resources where she enjoys thorny digital preservation issues, and seeing all the amazing collections that exist around Australasia. She almost completed a PhD on preserving the musical instrument, the Trautonium.

Sarah Aldrich began working with Gaia Resources after a decade working in museums and archives in the US. She enjoys supporting the technical side of the systems she once relied upon. Sarah has a Masters degree in Byzantine Art History as well as diplomas in Museology and Information Technology.

Piers Higgs is the founder and CEO of Gaia Resources. He has a keen interest in archives and collections, and has led the development of capability and capacity in this area within Gaia Resources, who now provide services to these organisations across Australia.

